

INFLUENCE OF TENNIS COACHES ON ATHLETES' SELF-EFFICACY

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the influence of tennis coaches on athletes' self-efficacy. The quantitative research methodology was used to describe the characteristics of tennis athletes from different universities and analyzes the level of coaches' self-efficacy as well as the level of athletes' self-efficacy. Using a researcher-made questionnaire as the main instrument, divided into three sections, the study investigated the associations between coaches' and athletes' level of confidence, social skills, and decision-making abilities, which influence tennis playing efficacy, as well as athletes' self-efficacy. Key findings revealed that tennis athletes demonstrated high, low and very low competitiveness at institutional, regional, national and international levels across different playing and performances. Coaches demonstrated very high level of confidence, social skills and decision-making abilities. Athletes demonstrated high level of confidence, social skills and decision-making. Significant difference was revealed on the confidence and decision-making ability and no significant difference in their social skills. There were no significant relationships on coaches and athletes' confidence and social skills. Significant relationship was revealed in the decision making and self-efficacy of coaches and athletes. Finally, given the findings of the study, it is recommended that an individualized development plan be developed for each athlete. For coaches, it is recommended that regular capacity building trainings be conducted, especially in the areas of confidence, social skill and decision-making abilities.

Keywords: *Athletes, confidence, decision -making, influence, self-efficacy, social skills, tennis coaches*

INTRODUCTION

Tennis conveys the concepts of fairness, wisdom, etiquette, and civilization to people, and these concepts continue to guide people in their thoughts and behaviors to continue to carry forward this noble quality of will and cultivate the excellent qualities of honesty and trustworthiness, modesty and prudence for teachers and students. Moreover, there is evidence that tennis coaches in universities are perceived as responding differentially to more and less successful students (Fletcher & Roberts, 2019). With the development of the times and the progress of society, people are paying more and more attention to sports, even though tennis has caught the attention of university students and athletes. At present, only a limited number of universities offer tennis teaching courses.

A higher-performing athlete rated their coaches as engaging in significantly higher levels of training and instruction in universities as having a more democratic and a less autocratic decision-making style, as being more socially supportive, and as offering more positive feedback than did lower-status athletes labeled “survivors” by their coaches (Chelladurai, 2020). Important qualities have a subtle guidance and education function for coaches and players in school, making them develop in the right and healthy direction of life, and educating them to respect others, respect themselves and obey discipline, which is consistent with the guidance and education function of campus culture, therefore, tennis can promote the guidance and education function of campus culture (Smith, Smoll, & Hunt, 2022). Moreover, tennis is an elegant sport, which combines sports and aesthetic teaching in one. On the one hand, tennis is played one-on-one, and students may prefer to meet more friends and join the sport together. On the other hand, tennis requires a great deal of skill, which demands the strategic skills of the participants. Engagement in group physical activities, sports, and games emerges as a cost-effective strategy known to enhance socialization skills and overall social well-being among individuals diagnosed with ASD (Coffee, 2019). For instance, such involvement has been associated with improvements in assertiveness, self-control, and self-esteem linked to physical prowess and appearance (Rees, 2019).

Nazarudin et al. (2019) found that the relationship between confidence and self-efficacy was particularly significant in decision-making and social skills. This further emphasizes the importance of developing self-confidence in athletes and coaches to promote higher levels of self-efficacy. Nohria and Khurana (2020) found that coaches' self-efficacy directly influenced athletes' performance. This is consistent with the notable association between coach and athlete self-efficacy in the present study, furthering understanding that coaches play a key role in athlete's performance.

The theory of achievement goal emphasizes the purpose and significance of actions directed toward goals based on individuals' definitions of success and their evaluations of whether they have displayed competence, decision-making skills, confidence, and social abilities with peers (Kauffmann, 2020). At the core of the theory are two key concepts: individual goal orientations, which steer perceptions of

achievement and behavior, and the motivational atmosphere established within achievement environments (Kellett et al., 2021).

The theory delineates two distinct understandings of success manifested in mastery (task) and ego achievement goal orientations. In mastery orientation, success is internally referenced and defined through personal advancement, enjoyment, exertion, and learning from errors (Lyle, 2019).

Self-efficacy, first introduced by psychologist Albert Bandura, is one of the core concepts in social cognitive theory. It is defined as an individual's level of confidence and belief in accomplishing a specific task, a belief that he or she can achieve goals and overcome difficulties. The concept of self-efficacy profoundly shapes an individual's behaviors, thinking, and emotions, influencing their performance in various domains (Rogers, 2019). Self-efficacy significantly influences athletes' goal setting and pursuit. Athletes with high self-efficacy often establish ambitious goals and show greater willingness to exert effort in their pursuit (Zhan, 2019). This level of self-efficacy not only improves an individual's motivation, but also enables them to better cope with the stress and competition of the game. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to try and persist in achieving goals in the face of difficulties. In contrast, individuals with low self-efficacy may be more likely to give up due to frustration. An individual's level of self-efficacy also influences the goals they set. Individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to set more challenging and attainable goals. Self-efficacy is also closely related to emotional state. A more positive emotional state usually accompanies high self-efficacy, whereas low self-efficacy can lead to depression and anxiety.

In this study, self-efficacy theory can be used to explain and explore how coaching affects athletes' self-efficacy. Through mentoring, motivation, providing support, and positive feedback, coaches can shape an athlete's confidence and belief in their ability to succeed in tennis. By understanding players self-efficacy in different contexts, coaches can provide targeted psychological support to help them overcome difficulties, increase confidence, and improve their level of performance in the game. Coaches can set reasonable goals and train programmers according to the athletes' self-efficacy level to motivate them to fulfill their potential better and improve their overall self-efficacy. Hence, this paper aimed to investigate if tennis coaching can strengthen the confidence of player in improving confidence, social skills and decision-making skills.

Research Questions

To give light to the problem, the researchers sought to answer the influence of the coaches on the self-efficacy of Tennis athletes.

1. What is the tennis athletes' performance level when group as to:
 - 1.1 Institutional;
 - 1.2 Regional;
 - 1.3 National; and
 - 1.4 International?
2. What is the level of efficacy of coaches' and athletes when grouped as to:

- 2.1 Confidence;
 - 2.2 Social Skills; and
 - 2.3 Decision-Making Skills?
3. Is there a significant difference in the coaches and athletes' self-efficacy in terms of:
- 3.1 Confidence;
 - 3.2 Social Skills; and
 - 3.3 Decision-Making?
4. Is there a significant relationship between coaches' and athletes' self-efficacy in terms of?
- 4.1 Confidence;
 - 4.2 Social Skills; and
 - 4.3 Decision-Making?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research questions posted, the following hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the coaches' and athletes' self-efficacy in terms of confidence; social skills; decision-making.

Ho2: There is no Is there a significant relationship between coaches' and athletes' self-efficacy in terms of confidence; social skills; decision-making.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used quantitative research. It involved the collection, processing, testing and analysis of information in order to draw meaningful conclusions. Survey research, an important tool in various quantitative research approaches, involves administering questionnaires to respondents to collect data.

Research Locale and Participants

The respondents for this study came from the total of 1200 tennis athletes in Asia, and a sample size of 300 served as the respondents of the study while 50 coaches willingly joined the investigation.

Research Instrument

The researcher-made questionnaire undergo validation with 5 experts in the field physical education. The coaches' self-efficacy questionnaire was used, which was divided into two parts. The coaches' profile and coaches' self-efficacy. Self-efficacy included, social skills, and decision-making skills. The athletes' questionnaire was divided into two parts. The athlete's profile and the athlete self-efficacy, social skills and decision-

making skills. The last part deals on coaches and athlete' performance. After getting the validity, a reliability test was conducted 20 persons who are not part of the actual respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

The instrument assessed for validity and reliability using Cronbach Alpha. After an excellent result was obtained the necessary permission from the university president to conduct the study to the athletes. Samples were randomly selected from the target population using appropriate statistical methods during the data collection stage. Data collection and processing procedures were carefully planned to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data. Subsequently, quantitative data analyses were conducted.

Data Analysis

The study follows the ethical standard of research. After gathering all the data, the researchers used the Weighted Mean, Frequency and Percentage, ANOVA and Pearson Product Moment of Correlation was used.

RESULTS

This part includes the discussion of results.

Table 1 *Computed Weighted Mean and standard deviation on the Level of Tennis Athletes' Performance*

	Mean	SD	VI
Institutional	2.50	.85	High
Regional	2.22	.94	Low
National	1.80	.99	Low
International	1.74	1.00	Very Low
Over all	2.00	.94	Low

Note. Scale 1.00-1.74 Very low; 1.75-2.49 Low; 2.50-3.24 high; 3.25-4.00 very High

Table 2 *Computed Weighted Mean and standard deviation on the Level of Efficacy of Coaches and Athletes*

COACHES	Mean	SD	VI
Confidence	3.72	.30	Very High
Social Skills	3.68	.26	Very High
Decision-Making	3.78	.19	Very High
Over All	3.72	.25	Very High
ATHLETES	Mean	SD	VI
Confidence	2.86	.30	High

Social Skills	3.11	.26	High
Decision-Making	2.92	.09	High
Over All	2.96	.22	High

Note. Scale 1.00-1.74 Very low; 1.75-2.49 Low; 2.50-3.24 high; 3.25-4.00 very High

Table 3 Differences in the Level of Self-Efficacy when they are grouped according to coaches and athletes, confidence, social skills and decision making

INDICATORS	Group	Mean	SD	T-value	P-value	Ho	VI
Confidence	coaches	3.72	.17	2.423	.01	Rejected	Significant
	athletes	2.83	.11				
Social Skills	coaches	3.68	.17	1.696	.09	Accepted	Not Significant
	athletes	3.11	.09				
Decision Making	coaches	3.78	.20	2.322	.02	Rejected	Significant
	athletes	2.92	.09				

Table 4 Significant Relationship on the efficacy of coaches' and athletes' when grouped as confidence, social skills, decision making

		Coaches' Confidence	Coaches' Social Skills	Coaches' Decision-Making	Coaches' Self-Efficacy
Athletes' Confidence	r	0.87	0.22	0.69	0.74
	sig	0.05	0.72	0.20	0.15
	Ho	Rejected	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted
	VI	Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant
Athletes' Social Skills	r	0.90	0.40	0.81	0.87
	sig	0.04	0.50	0.10	0.05
	Ho	Rejected	Rejected	Accepted	Rejected
	VI	Significant	Significant	Not Significant	Significant
Athletes' Decision Making	r	0.74	0.41	0.71	0.76
	sig	0.16	0.49	0.18	0.13
	Ho	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted
	VI	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant
Athletes' Self-Efficacy	r	0.93	0.35	0.80	0.86
	sig	0.02	0.56	0.10	0.06
	Ho	Rejected	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted
	VI	Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the statistical results specifically the weighted mean and the standard deviation of the tennis athletes' performance at the institutional, regional, national, and international levels. The highest mean was their institutional performance with a weighted mean of 2.50 at high performance and the lowest mean was the international level with a weighted mean of 1.74 as a very low performance. Wang, et al. (2019) found that achieving good rankings in interscholastic competitions is closely related to individual skill level, match experience, and tactical use. Excellent rankings usually indicate that athletes have achieved significant success in intramural competitions, which can enhance their self-efficacy. Pilus and Saadan (2019) studied that higher weekly training hours were positively associated with athletes' skill level and match performance. Over the long term, high-intensity training contributes to improved skill levels, endurance, and competition adaptability. This is consistent with the higher mean values in this indicator, suggesting that athletes are more invested in in-school training. Liu et al. (2023) showed that these honors could increase an athlete's self-esteem and self-efficacy, affecting his/her future performance. Therefore, high mean values of this indicator are associated with positive achievement motivation in athletes. Gall et al. (2021) found that experienced athletes are more likely to perform well in high-pressure situations. Therefore, the medium mean for this indicator reflects some competitive experience for participants in intramural leagues.

Table 2 presents the level of efficacy of coaches and athletes. The coaches highest weighted mean was decision making and the lowest weighted mean was social skills, still all are in the very high level. For the tennis athletes, the highest means was 3.11 the social skills and the lowest mean was confidence at 2.86 all in High level. Over all mean for coaches was 3.72 as very high level and 2.96 for tennis athletes as high level. Mageau (2019) showed that coaches' confidence and trust in their teaching methods directly affect athletes' learning and skill enhancement. When coaches are confident in their approach, they are more effective in imparting knowledge and skills, improving athletes' overall performance. Coaches also showed very high level of confidence in "I am confident that I can handle difficult situations." This is consistent with the day-to-day demands on coaches to deal with the challenges and pressures of competitive sports. Tschannen et al. (2020) showed that having the confidence to deal with stressful and difficult situations enhances a coach's leadership and team management skills. Mageau (2019) showed that coaches' confidence and trust in their teaching methods directly affect athletes' learning and skill enhancement. When coaches are confident in their approach, they are more effective in imparting knowledge and skills, improving players' overall performance. The study by Demers et al. (2020) showed that individualized training programmers based on the performance and needs of the players are essential in improving the skill level and overall performance. The indicators in the Table emphasize the confidence and competence of coaches in this regard. In sports, unexpected situations and emergencies occur between rapid changes.

The coach's ability to make the right decisions quickly in these situations is critical to the success of the team (Jones, 2020). Gao & Yang (2022) showed that an athlete's

confidence in his or her skills is closely related to his or her performance in competition. Athletes with high self-efficacy are more inclined to set higher goals, face challenges more positively, and better maintain their composure when faced with stress (Jowett, 2021). Therefore, the results reflect that athletes maintain a high level of confidence in all aspects of the game, which positively affects their performance in competition. Myers et al. (2020) showed that maintaining positive competitive relationships and respect helps to increase athletes' motivation to play, making them more competitive and confident in defeating their opponents. Rodriguez et al. (2021) concluded that harmony and cooperation within a team are essential to improve the team's performance. Good social skills can lead to better conflict management among team members and ensure harmonious team functioning.

Table 3 presents the significant difference on the level of self-efficacy of coaches and athletes when grouped as to confidence and decision making with p value of .01 and .02 which is significant. Social skills at .09 not significant. Coaches showed significant strengths in self-confidence and decision-making ability. These findings provide useful information for developing individualized training programmers and improving team effectiveness. Brackenridge (2021) showed that coaches' self-efficacy is strongly related to athletes' performance and team success, as athletes tend to be positively influenced by coaches' confidence. Coaches are more self-confident in establishing effective communication and teamwork. Good social skills are essential for team cohesion and collaboration among athletes, which is widely supported in past research (Balague, 2019). Findings in terms of decision-making skills reveal that coaches are more confident and better at making key decisions quickly during games. This is consistent with coaches taking on strategic leadership roles in games, whereas athletes focus more on execution and individual decision-making (Cushion et al., 2019).

Table 4 shows the relationship between coaches' and athletes' self-efficacy in terms of confidence, social skills, and decision-making ability. These relationships are presented through correlation coefficients (r) and significance levels (sig). In terms of confidence, the relationship between coaches and athletes was not statistically significant, meaning there was no significant association between the confidence levels of coaches and athletes in this study. However, there was a significant relationship between coaches and athletes in terms of social skills and decision-making skills, suggesting some correlation between coaches' and athletes' levels of self-efficacy in these two areas. There was a significant positive correlation between coaches and athletes in terms of self-efficacy. Specifically, the correlation coefficients (r) between coaches' self-efficacy and athletes' self-efficacy were 0.86 and 0.74, respectively, and the p-values under each indicator were less than 0.05, indicating that these correlations were significant. This indicates that the level of coach's self-efficacy is closely related to the level of athlete's self-efficacy, and it is possible that the coach's confidence, social skills, and decision-making ability have a certain influence and contribute to the athlete's self-efficacy.

In terms of social skills, although there is also a positive correlation between coaches' and athletes' social skills, the correlation is not significant. Although the correlation

coefficient is 0.40, the p-value is greater than 0.05, This could mean that the level of social skills of the coach does not directly affect the level of social skills of the athletes.

In terms of decision-making skills, not significant. The correlation coefficient is 0.71, the p-value is greater than 0.05, This suggests that the level of the coach's decision-making ability influence on the athletes' decision-making ability. Research on decision-making skills has emphasized the importance of coaches' decision-making in competition for athletes' performance (Liang & Xu, 2023). The coach's level of decision-making not only affects the athlete's confidence, but is also directly related to the team's success (Courneya & Chelladurai, 2021).

In terms of self-efficacy, the relationship between coaches and athletes was also significant. The correlation coefficient was 0.86, there was a relationship between a coach's and an athlete's self-efficacy.

These results have important implications for understanding the interactions and influences between coaches and athletes. They can help provide insight into how overall team performance can be improved by increasing levels of self-efficacy in specific areas. Although coaches' and athletes' self-efficacy were generally correlated, there were differences in specific aspects. This suggests that the interactions between coaches and athletes may differ across different aspects of self-efficacy, which requires more in-depth research and understanding.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the researcher came up with the following conclusions. At institutional, regional, national, and international levels, tennis players demonstrated high, low and very low competitiveness levels across different playing performances. Coaches demonstrate high levels of confidence, social skills and decision-making, showing a wealth of expertise and skills in teaching and match management. Athletes demonstrate high levels of confidence, social skills, decision-making ability, showing that they have strong confidence in their abilities and can participate actively and make informed decisions within the team. Coaches were significantly higher than athletes in confidence, social skills, and decision-making ability due to their professional background and leadership roles. Therefore, hypotheses number 1, on confidence and decision making was rejected, while on social skills is accepted. By analyzing the relationship between coach and athletes' self-efficacy, they found congruence between the two in terms of self-efficacy and decision-making. Therefore, hypotheses No 2 on coaches and athletes' confidence and social skills was rejected, while on decision making and self-efficacy hypotheses was accepted. This provides important clues for an in-depth study of coach-athlete interactions, influences, and training programmers.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions derived from this study, the following are the recommendations:

The School Administrators should analyze the performance of tennis athletes and coaches, more effective training and development strategies can be formulated for a successful training program.

The Physical Education Teachers. It is recommended that regular capacity-building training be conducted, particularly in the areas of confidence, social skills, and decision-making ability. Improving the coaching team's overall quality will help guide and develop better players.

The Tennis Athletes an individualized development plans be developed for each athlete. Programs should be based on athletes' level of performance at the international, national, regional, and institutional levels, focusing on their weaknesses and providing targeted technical, tactical, and psychological training.

The Future Researchers. To enhance tennis athletes' performance on the international stage, it is recommended that sports organizations actively promote international exchange and cooperation. By participating in international training programs and exchange activities, players can be exposed to different levels of competition and improve their international competitiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers sought an approval from the university administrators/heads. After the approval, getting the permission from the coaches, trainers' and athletes to conduct the questionnaire. The researchers guaranteed that all the data gathered from the respondents remained confidential. Moreover, trust which implies that the respondents should be protected all the time.

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